

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Bekarian**FIRST NAME:** Mary**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-10)
2. Plagiarism Awareness (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35-37)
3. Referencing and Citation (EUCLID, n.d.)
4. Paragraph Structure and Clarity (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-50)
5. American Versus British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)

BASICS OF DOCTORAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is a fundamental skill for scholars and professionals, especially in the field of international public health. The first period of the ACA-401D module on International Academic Writing has provided critical insights into the principles and key features of a comprehensive academic essay. The course pack covered the characteristics of well-organized writing, appropriate referencing, plagiarism avoidance, and paragraph consistency. This response paper reflects my takeaways from the course material and the importance of these guidelines in both my studies and professional growth.

2) ACADEMIC WRITING PRINCIPLES

The first chapter of the course material demonstrated the key factors and essential steps for writing an academic essay that will serve the purpose (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-10). In addition, I read the Academic Writing Guide prepared by Anne Whitaker, particularly The Writing Process chapter (Whitaker 2009, 4-19), to combine and benefit from the information for future use.

Both materials emphasized the importance of understanding the topic of the assignment and planning ahead to have a high-quality outcome in the required timeframe. I understood the significance of doing extensive research to have the answers to the question, valuable evidence to support different arguments, and enough data to analyze.

The structure of the essay also matters in organizing the flow and making it understandable for the reader. As per EUCLID requirements, the essay should have an introduction, a body, and a conclusion (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10). The main purpose of the introduction is to start with the general content and narrow it down to the specific topic of the paper, moving to the body where the critique of the existing knowledge and the evidence-based discussion is presented, to summarizing the key points and the final statement in conclusion.

3) PLAGIARISM AWARENESS

Oxford University defined Plagiarism in Oxford University Press (University of Oxford 2019) as follows:

Plagiarism is the act of using someone else's words, ideas, or work without proper acknowledgment, presenting them as one's own. It includes direct copying, paraphrasing without citation, and failing to credit sources in academic, professional, or creative work. Plagiarism is considered a serious ethical violation in scholarly writing.

This course made me aware of different forms of plagiarism and equipped me with the detecting tools and best practices to avoid it. Furthermore, it is necessary to distinguish between summarizing, quoting, and paraphrasing. I learned that we could use a statement as it is with the exact words of the author by using quotation marks (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35–37). However, in my opinion, excessive quoting can reduce the quality of the paper. Instead, correct paraphrasing, while reflecting the original idea of the author, can be used to demonstrate integrated knowledge of original content and evidence-based discussion.

4) REFERENCING AND CITATION

Referencing sources correctly is essential for maintaining academic integrity and ensuring that arguments are well-supported by credible research. Before engaging with my master's degree program, I found referencing it to be a technical process used to summarize previous research in an introduction of a new research paper; however, I now recognize it as a critical element of scholarly work that demonstrates respect for intellectual property and enhances the credibility of my writing.

The guidance provided through the documents and videos in my EUCLID LMS has improved my ability to acknowledge existing work and incorporate sources more effectively, ensuring accuracy and consistency in my work (EUCLID, n.d.). This module

has highlighted the role of referencing as a fundamental component of ethical scholarship that supports the validity and transparency of academic essays.

5) PARAGRAPH STRUCTURE AND CLARITY

Another important lesson from this module is the importance of clear and well-structured paragraphs. Robust and high-quality academic writing requires logical organization, topic sentences, and smooth transitions between ideas. Before studying this material, I often struggled with paragraph length and consistency, sometimes including multiple ideas in a single paragraph. Now, I will be structuring my writing to enhance readability and logical flow as per what was advised in the course material (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40). Implementing these techniques will allow me to communicate complex ideas more effectively in my papers without overwhelming the reader.

A well-structured paragraph should have a clear topic sentence that introduces the main idea, followed by supporting evidence and analysis. Additionally, transitions between paragraphs should be seamless, avoiding unnecessary repetition or overly complex phrasing.

The first period of ACA-401D emphasized the necessity of using standardized abbreviations, accepted terminology, and a structured format, including chronological numbering, headings, and subheadings, to enhance clarity and organization in academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 44–50).

6) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

My previous reports and assignments contained a mix of American and British English. It was only after reading this course's material that I realized the impact of consistent spelling on the quality of deliverables. I discovered that the differences between US and UK English extend beyond just spelling; they also include variations in punctuation, vocabulary, and date format. Understanding this distinction is essential for maintaining clarity and consistency in the academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24–32).

7) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401D module has significantly enriched my understanding of academic writing, from referencing and plagiarism avoidance to paragraph structure and clarity. By applying these principles, I aim to improve my writing proficiency, maintain academic integrity, and communicate ideas more effectively.

Beyond academia, effective writing strengthens credibility in public health, ensuring research findings are accessible to policymakers and practitioners. The

knowledge gained through this module will not only strengthen my academic abilities but also enable me to make meaningful contributions to the field of international public health.

Pursuing my doctoral degree after obtaining my master's was a challenging decision, especially while balancing house chores, a full-time job, caring for my older daughter, and raising my newborn. As I continue my studies and professional journey, I am committed to producing high-quality, impactful work. This module has reinforced the importance of refining my writing skills and reminded me of the value of my work in shaping healthier populations and making meaningful contributions to the field of public health.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. N. d. "ACA-401D: International Academic Writing (Doctorate) – EUCLID University // EULER University LMS." Accessed February 5, 2025. <https://eucliduniversity.net/courses/aca-401d/>.

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